

O'ZBEKISTON TARIXIDA Z.M. BOBUR SHAXSIYATI

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Farg'ona viloyati Oltiariq tumani 2 son kasb
hunar maktabi tarix fani o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Maqolada o'zbek tarixi va adabiyotida o'z o'rniga ega bo'lgan zahiriddin muhammad boburning xayot yo'li va uning o'zbek davlatchiligi tarixidagi ahamiyatiga qisqacha to'xtab o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Bobur, hukmdor, kurash, Vatan, sog'inch.

Аннотация: Кратко рассмотрен жизненный путь Захириддина Мухаммеда Бабура, занявшего свое место в истории и литературе Узбекистана, его значение в истории узбекской государственности.

Ключевые слова: Бабур, правитель, борьба, Родина, тоска.

Abstract: The article briefly discusses the life path of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, who has a place in Uzbek history and literature, and his significance in the history of Uzbek statehood.

Keywords: Babur, ruler, struggle, Homeland, nostalgia.

Bobur o'zbek tarixida tom ma'noda yirik shaxs. Uning tarixchi olim, zukko adib va dilbar shoir sifatida qoldirgan adabiy merosi bebahodir. Bobur hukmdorlik majburiyatlaridan ortib yirik asarlar yozishga muvaffaq bo'lgan. Uning lirikasi adabiyotdagi o'ziga xos lirika. SHubhasiz, she'riyatining asosiy mavzui Vatan, Vatan sog'inchi bo'lgan. Taxt uchun qondosh aka-ukalarning dushman bo'lib kurashishi, atrofdagi insonlarning xiyonati, vatanini birlashtirolmaganidan so'ng tortgan azoblari va nihoyat umrining so'ngigigacha Vatan sog'inchi uning

she'riyatiga ko'chgan desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Bu mavzular Bobur g'azallari, ruboiylarida keng yoritilgan.

Bobur 1483 yili 14 fevralda Andijon shahrida, Farg'ona ulusining hokimi Umarshayx Mirzo va asli chingiziylardan bo'lgan malika Qutlug' Nigor Xonim oilasida dunyoga keladi. “Bobur” so'zi forsiy tilidan “babr”, ya'ni “bars”, “yo'lbars” degan ma'noni bildiradi. Boburning otasi Umarshayx Mirzo Sohibqiron Amir Temur avlodidan. Amir Temurning uchinchi o'g'li Mironshoh Mirzoning evarasi bo'lgan. Boburning onasi Qutlug' Nigor-Xonim mo'g'ul xonlaridan biri YUnusxonning qizi bo'lgan.

Barcha shahzodalar singari Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur ta'lim va tarbiyani otasining saroyida oladi. Biroq otadan juda erta yetim qoladi. 1494 yili Umarshayx Mirzo baxtsiz hodisa tufayli vafot etadi. 12 yoshida Bobur otasining o'rniga taxtga o'tirishga majbur bo'ldi. U hukmdor bo'lgan dastlabki yillarda Temuriy shahzodalar o'rtasida toju taxt uchun ayovsiz kurash avj oladi. YOsh Zahiriddin Andijon taxti uchun amakisi Sulton Ahmad Mirzo hamda ukasi Jahongir Mirzo bilan kurashishiga to'g'ri keladi. Bobur ukasi bilan murosaga kelishga harakat qiladi Jahongir Mirzoga Farg'ona ulusini ikkiga taqsimlab, yarmini topshiradi. O'zi esa Samarqand uchun bo'layotgan kurashlarga kirishadi.

Kurashlar hech qanday natija bermaydi, unda katta harbiy kuchga ega bo'lgan SHayboniyxonning qo'li baland keladi. Bobur Samarqandni tashlab ketadi. Biroq SHayboniyxon 1504 yili Andijonni ham qo'lga kiritadi va Bobur janub tomon bosh olib ketishga majbur bo'ladi. Kobul ulusida o'z hokimiyatini o'rnatadi. 1505-1515 yillar davomida u Markaziy Osiyoga qaytishga harakat qiladi, biroq bu urinishlaridan ham hech narsa chiqmaydi.

Bobur o'z mavqeini tiklash maqsadida 1519-1525 yillarda Hindiston uchun bir necha bor janglar olib boradi. 1526 yil Panipatda Hindiston sultoni Ibrohim Lo'di bilan jang qiladi. 1527 yili esa CHitora hokimi Rano Sango bilan kurashadi. Ikki kurashda ham Boburning qo'li baland keladi. SHu tariqa Bobur Hindistonda

o'z hokimiyatiga asos soladi. Bobur asos solgan sulola tarixda eng yirik sulolalardan biri bo'lib, uning avlodlari 350 yildan ortiq Hindistonga hukmronlik qiladi.

Bobur hukmronligi davrida Hindiston gullab-yashnaydi. Adabiyot, san'at, shaharsozlik rivojlanadi. Uning o'g'illari va avlodlari davrida Hindiston qudratli mamlakatlardan biriga aylandi. Boburning avlodlari bobosining bunyodkorlik ishlarini munosib davom ettirishadi. Mamlakatda mukammal ma'naviy-ruhiy muhit vujudga keladi. Hindiston tarixida Boburning ahamiyati nihoyatda katta. Yirik hind olimi Javoharlal Neru u haqida shunday deydi: “Bobur Hindistonga kelgandan keyin katta siljishlar yuz berdi va yangi rag'batlantirishlar hayotga, san'atga, arxitekturaga toza havo baxsh etdi, madaniyatning boshqa sohalari esa bir-birlariga tutashib ketdi”.

Bulardan so'ng Bobur uzoq yashamadi: 1530 yili Agrada 47 yoshida vafot etadi. Rivoyatlarga ko'ra, Boburning to'ng'ich o'g'li Humoyun Mirzo og'ir dardga chalinadi. Bobur uch kechayu uch kunduz Yaratgandan o'g'lining dardiga shifo so'rab, farzandi chekayotgan dardni o'ziga berishini so'raydi. Humoyun Mirzo tuzaladi, biroq Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur ko'p o'tmay vafot etadi.

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